

Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 2

**Production-mode simulation with NEMO,
ICON-ESM, ECMWF, EC-Earth, IPSL model
Milestone MS2**

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Type: Report

Dissemination level: Public

Delivery date Annex 1 (DoA): Project month 36

Means of verifications: Production-mode simulation up and running

Achieved: Yes

If not achieved, indicate forecast achievement date: -

Comments: We have documented the current progress during the implementation of the production mode simulations on supercomputers of the consortium in deliverable D1.1 (<https://zenodo.org/record/5795991>) which is submitted together with this Milestone document. The model development teams are making good progress when preparing the model configurations for the pre-exacscale EuroHPC systems. We now hope to be able to get access to those machines soon, to make the final scalability tests in 2022.

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